

CASE STUDY ON UNTRAINED TEACHERS IN SCHOOLS (ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS) IN JIND AND HISAR DISTRICTS OF HARYANA

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Abstract:

Education is the means of self-realisation and self expression. It helps bringing out the best in a person. It promotes physical, intellectual, social, emotional and spiritual development of human beings. Education is felt essential for success of democracy and for bringing about desirable changes for all round development. Centre and state governments are doing lot of efforts to raise educational standards, despite lot of interventions the desired quality in education is yet not achieved. There are many shortcomings and imbalances. Not only social and economic inequalities are responsible for this, skilled and trained human resource is also lacking. I did survey in some rural and urban schools of Haryana (especially Jind and Hisar districts) to know the various aspects of pre-primary and primary schooling. In the research work I have included the untrained teacher resource, school infra, teaching learning materials and various teaching methodologies used in rural and urban schools and other aspects of pre-primary and primary schooling. In my survey I found that teachers blame poor parenting for dismal learning standards in schools. But according to me poorly trained teachers and social attitudes is the real problem. Teaching methodologies followed by teachers are still old. Innovative and creative teachers are lacking in all schools. Some teachers even don't know the exact definition of teaching methodologies. Learning attitude is missing from teacher side, but is expected from student side. D.Ed. or B.Ed. course don't prepare the teacher for real classroom teaching. In job teacher training session should be conducted on regular basis to train teacher for multi grade teaching methodologies. Cognitive development based, joyful and structured elementary curriculum is missing in all the schools.

Key Words: Teacher, Teaching Methodologies, Schools & Education.

Introduction:

Early childhood years are of crucial importance for the mental development of the child and possibly the ultimate level of development attained by an individual is determined by her experiences in the first five years of life. Practicing the right way to teach is the most important factor of every school. Therefore educationists all over the world have been struggling to develop methods that can optimize the attainment of teaching-learning objectives. Objective of every school should be to offer students maximum opportunities in a caring environment where they are enabled to reach their potential in all areas of school. According to Dr. Maria Montessori, "A child's work is to create the person she will become. Children are born with special mental powers which create the person she will become". But they cannot accomplish the task of self-construction without purposeful movement, exploration, and discovery of their environment. They must be given the freedom to use their inborn powers to develop physically, intellectually and spiritually. Preschool marks a new beginning for a child. It is a time for new experiences, discoveries, knowledge and challenges as a child leaves home to enter a new world of schooling. It is important to remember that each child is different and will learn and achieve in her own way. We must not compare them with other children but assess them by their own daily improvements.

Objectives of the Study:

- To know the scenario of pre-primary and primary education in this area.
- To know the teaching methodologies used by teachers in the elementary schools
- To know the teachers training/ update status
- To identify innovative teachers and schools
- To analyze the teachers attitude for teaching and training
- To suggest teacher training and innovative curriculum planning.

Limitations of the Study:

- The research is confined to limited area only.
- Time and resource constraint
- Data is questionnaire based so there may be some variation or biased from respondents.

Research Methodologies:

Four methods of data collection were employed for this study.

Table 1: Four methods of data collection were employed

Data Collection Method	Informant	Number
Face to face interactions	Principals	7
	Teachers	90
	Students	140
Questionnaires	Principals	11
	Teachers	115
Group discussions	Teachers	80
	Students	230
Workshops	Teachers	190

Summary:

I conducted trainings and survey in various schools in Hisar and Jind districts of Haryana, but the picture is not good. I prepared a questionnaire of 13 questions for the self assessment of the teachers and recorded the response from various schools.

Table 2: Following table is the analysis report of teachers self assessment questionnaire in 13 schools. (Round off value is shown)

Information on which analyzed	Percentage of Teachers
Teachers who demonstrate genuine interest in students and are responsive to their needs	73
Teachers who take constructive measures on concerns made by parents	60
Teachers who ensure all round development of all students and makes sure that no child is left behind when it comes to involve them in various activities.	53
Teachers who advise the students to solve their problems according to their needs	58
Teachers who use reward in class for achievement of desired aims	46
Teachers who use punishment in class for achievement of desired aims	63
Curriculum that teachers like	Short =31, Lengthy = 26, Rest of don't know
How much Teaching Learning Material teachers use in class	14% teacher use TLM, 27% use very less or only chalk and black board, rest of don't know what is TLM
Teachers who use needed remedial measures in teaching	76
Teachers who think other occupations are better than teaching	31
Teachers who has attended teacher's training programme by CBSE or other training agencies	19
Teachers whose students enjoy their teaching	36

In early education children have a stage to learn language skills. Listening is the first language skill that toddler should be exposed.

Chart 1: It shows the number of teacher who teaches writing as first language skill, Reading as second language skill and then succeeding speaking and listening.

This survey was conducted by giving a simple comprehension to all students in both the languages and by oral daily life situations. Literate parents also helped in this survey of language and mathematics skills.

Chart 2: Following chart shows the average weakness of primary students in reading, writing languages and basic mathematic skills.

Findings:

- Students are poor in basic language and mathematics skills.
- Even the medium of instruction is English, basic English language skills of the students are weak.
- The nation builder itself are unskilled. Teaching methodologies used by the teachers are old and boring for students.
- Most of teachers don't understand the reason behind academic weakness of the students.
- Most of the teacher never attended any in job training session.
- Most of the schools are deficient in TLM and other needed infra for joyful pedagogies.
- Attitude of the teachers is reluctant for trainings and CPD programmes.

Conclusions:

- Teachers get training for a government job only.
- Teacher's attitude for teaching – learning process is reluctant. Somewhere learning attitude is missing from teacher side, but is expected from student side.
- On the job training and CPD's are unavailable.
- There is insufficient infra and teaching learning material in schools.
- Teaching is not top service of the country, lack of government policy is responsible for unavailability of quality teachers.

Suggestions:

- Teacher should be trained on multi-grade teaching techniques.
- Good quality infra and Teaching-Learning material.
- Government should frame the policy to develop and retain effective teachers. Teaching should be top service of the country.

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